

HISTORY AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE MANAGEMENT DISCIPLINE

Valijonov Nurillo Nodirbek o'g'li

Student of Fergana Polytechnic Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14914337>

Abstract. *The article discusses the history and development of the management field. The importance of studying and analyzing the management field, especially the organizational-economic, social, cultural-educational significance of management in the field of management, has been studied and methodologically studied.*

Keywords: *management, economics, organization, learning, development, sector, theoretical, practical, governance, cybernetics, school.*

ИСТОРИЯ И РАЗВИТИЕ УПРАВЛЕНЧЕСКОЙ ДИСЦИПЛИНЫ

Аннотация. *В статье рассматривается история и развитие управленческой дисциплины. Изучена и методологически исследована важность изучения и анализа управленческой дисциплины, особенно организационно-экономическое, социальное, культурно-образовательное значение менеджмента в сфере управления.*

Ключевые слова: *управление, экономика, организация, обучение, развитие, отрасль, теоретический, практический, управление, кибернетика, школа.*

In the context of the global financial and economic crisis, the issues of supporting enterprises in the real sector of the economy, first of all, are the modernization of production, expansion of cooperative relations, establishment of strong partnerships, and stimulation of domestic demand for products developed in our country. It is known that any type of activity is built on the basis of management, because in the implementation of this activity, measures to achieve the intended goal, distribute the tasks to be performed, control their execution, as well as protect the interests of participants in this activity, and incentive measures are organized and coordinated in the management process. In this regard, the existing system in the economy also has its influence on management. Management is the organization of incentives to attract people to conscious labor and entrepreneurship, to control their responsibility for work, to ensure that their knowledge and skills have a positive effect on their activities [1].

The concept of management in a narrow sense is the extent to which the planning, organizing, and control processes necessary to determine and achieve the goals of an organization are useful and effective, depending on the ability to correctly choose the direction of activity, make

decisions, and control its management and the course of this process. Management as a broad concept, as one of the world's theorists of management and organization, Peter F. Drucker, said, "Management is a special type of activity, an element that transforms an unorganized, chaotic mass into an effective and productive group, society, directed towards a common goal, and stimulates social change".

Management is an important influencing force not only within the enterprise, but also in the entire society, the state, leading it to its chosen path, goals and aspirations, transforming the economy into a strong, stable working mechanism. Management is a certain type of system, the effective functioning of which is ensured by the performance of a certain function by each element of the system.

Management appeared together with people. It was separated into an independent type of activity in the process of division of labor and cooperation. It is based on the need to organize and coordinate the activities of people in social production. One of them is the leader, that is, the managers, and the others are subordinate to them, that is, the managed. The problem of management was first introduced to the public by the ancient Egyptians, who 6 thousand years ago recognized the need for goal-oriented organization of human activities, their planning and control of their results, and raised the issue of decentralization of management.

In the 20th century BC, the king of Babylon, neighboring Egypt, Hammurabi, used documents on ceramic tablets and testimonies to establish the need for management and control, recognized the inadmissibility of transferring responsibility by officials to their subordinates, and legally determined the level of wages.

Ceramic tablets dating back to the third millennium BC contain information about commercial transactions and ancient Sumerian laws, which also indicate the existence of management practices there. In ancient times, a certain share was also given to management; 400 BC, Socrates formulated the principle of the universality of management. His contemporary, the Iranian king Cyrus, put forward the idea of the need for special research to encourage people to act, that is, motivation. He also considered the problem of developing management information and drawing up plans. A little later, in Greece, they were engaged in methods of performing labor operations and ensuring their uniformity. Plato formulated the principle of specialization. In 325 BC, Alexander the Great first organized a headquarters as a center for controlling military operations. Ancient organizations had a certain structure, in which the ranks of the manager were distinguished.

There were also large political organizations, the leaders of which were kings and generals.

There were also managers, storekeepers, drivers, supervisors, governors of regions and treasurers, who helped ensure the functioning of these organizations. Over the years, the management of many organizations became more precise and complex, and the organizations themselves became stronger and more stable. An example of this is the Roman Empire, which existed for hundreds of years. The Roman army, distinguished by a clear structure of management, divided into divisions consisting of generals and officers, and its legions marched victoriously through poorly organized European countries and Central Asian states. The conquered territories were given to governors subordinate to Rome, and roads were built to establish communication with Rome.

Almost all forms, character and structure of modern management can be traced back to ancient organizations that differ significantly from today's. Elements of management existed even during the period of slavery, but direct coercion and the threat of punishment prevailed as the main means of forcing labor. Later, with the development of social production, such labor showed its inherent inefficiency. It was replaced by the system of commissioned labor that arose in the bourgeois era. It was based on the use of a fundamentally different, instrumental mechanism of coercion, using material incentives and economic means to control labor. Merchant capitalism, which arose in a number of Western European countries 250 years ago, had a completely different basis - money capital. Instead of direct and armed forms of coercion, capitalism formed a market mechanism based on the exchange of measured values, which provided for formal personal independence and equality of exchange parties, and was used everywhere. Although management practice has been developing since ancient times and up to the 20th century, perhaps no one has thought about its systematic management. People were mainly interested not in how to manage organizations, but in how to make a lot of money and gain political power.

At the beginning of the 19th century, the English researcher R. Owen devoted much of his time to the problems of achieving organizational goals with the help of other people. He provided workers with better housing, improved their working conditions, developed a system for assessing the results of their labor, and encouraged good work through generous payments. These reforms were a unique breakthrough in the essence of human perception of reality and the role of the leader.

However, despite this, the entrepreneurs of that time saw little common sense in R. Owen's reforms, none of them followed him, since they were not interested in management.

In this regard, only in the 19th and 20th centuries did management become an independent branch of human knowledge, a science.

The American Joseph Wharton in 1881 first developed a management course for teaching in colleges. The American engineer F. Taylor published his book “Principles of Scientific Management” in 1911, which aroused general interest and for the first time recognized management as an independent field of science and research. These works were the first attempts to scientifically generalize accumulated experience and form the foundations of scientific management. They were a response to the needs of industrial development, which increasingly included such specific features as mass production and mass sales, large-capacity markets and the creation of large-scale organizations in the form of powerful corporations and joint-stock companies. Very large organizations felt an urgent need for rational organization of production and labor, for all departments and services, managers and performers to work clearly and interconnectedly in accordance with scientifically based principles, norms and standards. The Industrial Revolution in England was the primary force that initially stimulated interest in management. But the idea that management could contribute significantly to the development and success of an organization first emerged in America, the birthplace of modern management. At the beginning of the 20th century, during a period of rapid development, the United States was practically the only country where individuals could overcome the constraints of their origin and nationality and demonstrate their initiative and individual agency. Millions of Europeans immigrated to America, creating a huge labor market there. Almost from its inception, the United States has strongly supported the idea of education for all, which has contributed to an increase in the number of people intellectually capable of fulfilling various roles in business and management.

Transcontinental railroads turned America into the largest single market in the world. At that time, there was practically no state regulation of business, so successful entrepreneurs became monopolists (sole rulers). As a result, large industries and enterprises were created, and standardized methods were required for their management [2].

The emergence of management is associated with the following main conditions:

- ❖ the development of mechanized production, increasing demands on the manager, the inability of the owner and entrepreneur to overcome the difficulties of growing management;
- ❖ the emergence of a large number of market entities, their growth in size and strengthening of market relations;

❖ the growth of competition and the stability of the market economy, which justified the need for a professional approach to management;

❖ the emergence of large corporations and, accordingly, an increase in the volume and complexity of management work that can only be performed by a special apparatus of employees.

In a corporation, management is completely separated from the self-management of the owner - entrepreneur;

❖ as a result of the concentration of property among shareholders, new tasks for managing joint-stock capital arise;

❖ entrepreneurs' attempts to use the advantages of technology created during the industrial revolution;

❖ the desire of creative, curious groups of people to create effective methods of doing work.

Management should be studied in connection with the economic basis of society, taking into account both its organizational-technical and socio-economic aspects. The subject of management is the study of the laws (laws), principles and relationships of management at all levels of economic activity. Management relations are an integral part of socio-economic relations and take on various economic, organizational, social, labor, psychological and other forms.

From an economic point of view, management is, first of all, a system of managing all economic problems, managing people. From a social point of view, management is, first of all, satisfying the social requirements of labor collectives, educating a person. The technology of the management process is the practical work performed by the employees of the management apparatus. Thus, the management process is the coordinated and coordinated work of the head of the management apparatus and people to achieve the set goal. In a market economy, there are three forms of management: private, collective and state management. In the private form of management, the owner makes decisions alone and is responsible for all work. The positive side of this form is that the owner has the opportunity to fully control the progress of work, but the disadvantage is that the investment is not large and one person is obliged to perform various management tasks. The owner is personally responsible for the implementation of all management tasks: planning, organizing, motivating, losses, damages, etc. In order to avoid bankruptcy in a highly competitive environment, the owner must constantly increase his knowledge and improve his management methods, that is, change the ways of influencing employees in accordance with the current market situation.

Management is based on collective legal systems. Economic laws play an important role in the management system of the economy. The main principles of management are: autocracy and collegiality, scientificity, planning, improvement of management methods and systems.

Production planning is one of the main functions of management. Strategic and innovative management is the main direction for the development of modern management [3].

In Uzbekistan, during the transition to market relations, the form of state management is one of the main ones. Management of economic processes in Uzbekistan has deep historical roots.

As mentioned above, even before the formation of management as a science, there were great figures who successfully led a diverse complex group of people, who understood the essence and content of this process and applied it in practice, and who left their experience and views as a legacy to future generations, the study of which has a beneficial effect on the development of modern management science. The works of such individuals as Al-Khwarizmi, Abu Nasr Al-Farabi, Abu Ali ibn Sino (IX-X centuries), Yusuf Khos Khajib (XI-XII centuries), Amir Temur (XIII-XIV centuries), Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, Alisher Navoi (XV centuries) on management are still considered guidelines that can be used today. For example, “Kutadgu bilik”, “Temur tuzuklari” and others.

Over the past 33 years since the establishment of the Republic of Uzbekistan, laws adopted on market reforms, presidential decrees and resolutions, and decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers are aimed at introducing market mechanisms into the economy in our country.

The program of transferring the economy of Uzbekistan to market relations and forming market mechanisms based on the principles laid down by the First President of our Republic, Islam Karimov, was called the “Uzbek model” in a number of countries. This model withstood the global financial and economic crisis and created a solid foundation for the sustainable development of our country.

In the early 1950 s, the “new” school had a great influence on the development of management. It is characterized by the introduction of methods and techniques of the exact sciences into management - mathematical modeling of decision-making, mathematical logic, programming, mathematical modeling of economic processes. The formation of this school is associated with the development of cybernetics and the study of processes. The study of processes is associated with the mathematical modeling of management, the allocation of reserves, resources, replacement of obsolete equipment, and optimal planning. Later, an independent discipline was formed within the “new” school - the theory of management decision-making.

A brief description of the development of foreign management indicates that the search for new methods and forms of improving management continued unabated. The “new” school is a logical continuation of the “social systems” school [4].

Management is the organization of motivating people to conscious labor and entrepreneurship, controlling their responsibility for work, ensuring that their knowledge and skills have a positive impact on their activities, and encouraging them. The subject of this discipline is a set of theoretical and practical principles that express the forms and methods of organizing management in all areas of business. The effective management of this activity by a leader who has mastered and can apply management methods has a great impact not only on production, but also on the development of the entire economy. A manager is a qualified specialist who has undergone special training and has mastered the secrets and laws of management. A manager is a designated manager and belongs to a separate social stratum.

REFERENCES

1. D.S. Kasimova. Management Theory. Textbook. –Tashkent, “Tafakkur Bostoni”. 2011.
2. N. K. Yuldashev. Management. Textbook. –Tashkent, “National Society of Philosophers of Uzbekistan” Publishing House. 2018, pp. 5-8
3. M. B. Bekmuradov., Kh. Kh. Shodiev. “Management Theory and Practice”. Textbook for Masters. Tashkent – 2021. “Zamon Polygraph” Publishing House. p. 272.
4. A. Haydarov. “Planning and Management of Creative Activities” –Tashkent. “Kamalak” 2019.